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minimise their inflow into VAM

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document serves as a dossier on the Reduction of Methane Emissions (REM) project, which focuses on addressing the environmental challenges associated with abandoned mine methane (AMM) emissions. The REM project is integral to sustainable greenhouse gas management within the coal mining sector in support of a green deal economy. Its aim is to reduce costs related to the liquidation of coal mines and mitigate emissions of Coal Mine Methane (CMM) into the atmosphere.

The REM pilot and demonstration project will showcase intelligent management techniques for low-content AMM (less than 30% CH₄) located in post-mining goafs at the Pniówek underground coking coal mine. This will be accomplished through the identification and sealing of goaf zones, extraction of low-content AMM using advanced Long Reach Directional Drilling (LRDD) technology, and its transport through specially designed pipelines to a surface compressor station. The gas will then be used to feed engines specifically adapted for LCAMM, generating electricity and heat.

Additionally, ventilation air methane (VAM) emissions from mine shafts will be meticulously monitored and verified using the latest gas sensing technologies and unmanned aircraft systems (UAS). This innovative approach to managing the post-mining methane emission chain aims to significantly reduce VAM at underground coal mines in Poland and Romania, enhancing labor safety and decreasing the carbon footprint of coal mines. This effort contributes to the Global Methane Pledge goals for the energy sector.

The innovative techniques proposed in the REM project will be considered for international patents and can be replicated and scaled globally in other gassy coal mines. The project will be expertly managed by an international consortium that includes GIG, JSW, INiG, and PIG, members of the first International Center of Excellence on Coal Mine Methane (ICE CMM) under the UNECE Group of CMM experts.

2 PROBLEM OUTLINE

Methane stands out as a potent greenhouse gas, possessing a global warming potential (GWP) that is 28-36 times greater than that of CO₂ over a 100-year period (as noted by the IPCC in 2016 and US EPA in 2017). It is a key contributor to air pollution, aiding in the formation of ozone, which poses significant health risks. Methane has a relatively short lifespan in the atmosphere but has a GWP 84 times that of CO₂ over a 20-year period. Therefore, reducing methane emissions can quickly enhance air quality and mitigate climate change effects, all while leveraging methane's value as an energy resource for new business ventures.

In the European Union, agriculture accounts for 53% of anthropogenic methane emissions, with 26% from waste and 19% from the energy sector. Globally, coal mining activities are responsible for about 11% of methane emissions from human activities, according to U.S. EPA estimates from 2019. However, some researchers argue that methane emissions from fossil fuels are underestimated. Schwietzke et al., for instance, suggested that "fossil fuel methane emissions are 60-110% greater than current estimates" (2016), while Miller et al. indicated that global methane emissions might be 1.5 times higher than accounted for in U.S. inventories (2013).

Coal mine methane (CMM) refers to the methane gas associated with coal mining activities, which can be emitted either from the coal seam itself or surrounding gas-rich formations. The volume of CMM generated depends on various factors such as the coal mine's productivity, the gas content of the coal seam, operational practices, and geological conditions. CMM can be captured using engineered boreholes that enhance the mine's ventilation system or can be emitted into the mine and expelled through ventilation shafts. The management of these methane emissions is crucial for maintaining mine safety but also presents opportunities to harness this gas for energy production if properly captured and utilized.

Captured CMM is transported to the surface through specialized drainage systems, as highlighted in the UNECE's Best Practice Guidance for Effective Methane Drainage and Use in Coal Mines (2016). This methane-air mixture (40-50%) can serve as a ready-to-use fuel in gas engines for electricity and heat generation. This represents a "low hanging fruit" for energy utilization, contrasting with Ventilation Air Methane (VAM), which accounts for about 70% of methane released during mining. VAM must be safely diluted to concentrations of 0-0.75% and expelled with ventilation air. Although it can be used for combustion in thermal reactors, the process is economically viable only when ventilation air contains more than 0.5% methane. VAM installations generally exhibit low efficiency, making them less economically and technically favorable compared to gas engine systems.

Even after coal production stops or a mine is abandoned, methane, termed abandoned mine methane (AMM), continues to be released over time. Typically, AMM contains low concentrations of methane (LCAMM), usually less than 30% CH₄. The role of AMM in the total emissions from coal

mining is a frequent inquiry among CMM experts and practitioners, including partners in the REM project consortium, such as GIG, JSW SA, INiG, and PIG, who are part of the International Center of Excellence on Coal Mine Methane (ICE CMM) under UNECE. More insights into AMM and CMM emissions can be found in the work of UNECE experts, often referenced by the European Commission.

In light of these considerations, the REM pilot project aims to demonstrate the effective management of low-content AMM in the goafs of the "Pniówek" underground coking coal mine. This involves identifying and sealing goaf zones, extracting LCAMM with advanced Long Reach Directional Drilling (LRDD) technology, and transporting it through dedicated pipelines to a surface compressor station. The gas will then be processed in specialized gas engines adapted for LCAMM, producing electricity and heat. Additionally, VAM emissions from mine shafts will undergo monitoring and verification using the latest gas sensing technologies and unmanned aircraft systems (UAS). This novel management approach aims to substantially reduce VAM emissions at Polish and Romanian underground coal mines, significantly improving safety and lowering carbon footprints while contributing to the Global Methane Pledge goals for the energy sector.

The innovative techniques proposed by the REM project will seek international patents and can be replicated and scaled globally in gassy coal mines. The project is managed by an international consortium of experts and practitioners, including ICE CMM members. Their collaboration with the UNECE Group of Experts on Coal Mine Methane and Just Transition will ensure high-quality dissemination and utilization of the project outcomes.

3 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The objectives of REM are:

1. increased safety of miners - by removing significant volumes of AMM/VAM from underground workings,
2. significant climate change mitigation – by effective utilisation of captured AMM/VAM instead of venting it to the atmosphere,
3. better adaptation of coal mines to climate change – by emphasizing them/teaching them how effectively manage and control coal mine methane emissions,
4. more cost-effective activities of coal mines to smooth future phase-out transformation – by preparing lessons learnt document and training them based on REM project experience,
5. increased pollution prevention and control – by elaborating methodology to monitor VAM emissions through coal mines' shafts, increased motivation of coal mines' management to invest in CMM utilization - by demonstrating the real economic effects of the REM project based on the successful "Pniówek" mine example.

Following the above specific objectives the following **Key Performance Indicators** (KPI) are proposed:

1. Number of workers trained in the management and control of low content abandoned mine methane AMM (less than 30%) cumulated in post mining goafs and ventilation air methane (VAM).
2. Amount of effective methane utilisation from AMM emissions achieved in the project (difference between projected coal mine emissions from Pniówek Mine and emissions when implemented the REM project).
3. Number of tested/assessed series of solutions of which at least 3 of them demonstrate their cost-effectiveness, related to the technology used in REM, e.g., using latest Long Reach Directional Drilling (LRDD) technology, transporting Low Content AMM (LCAMM) using especially designed pipelines to the surface compressor station, feeding it into especially designed gas engines adjusted for LCAMM to produce electricity and heat.
4. Ranking of the efficient methods for an optimal measurement of VAM emissions from the underground coal mines return shafts and their comparison to the situation before implementing the project.
5. Number of managers trained on the business plan of CMM

4 METHODOLOGY

REM will be structured into four work packages (WP) in order to develop the methodology of the project in order to ensure a consistent approach. Apart from WP1 that addresses project's coordination and management, the rest of them are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. REM project WP2 methodology flow chart

Based on the EU Taxonomy Regulation 2020/852 the investment proposed under the REM project is environmentally sustainable, and its economic activity qualifies it as an environmentally sustainable because:

- (a) it contributes substantially to the following environmental objectives set out in Article 9 following Articles 10 to 16 of above-mentioned regulation:
- climate change mitigation;
 - climate change adaptation;
 - the transition to a circular economy;
 - pollution prevention and control;
 - the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems;
- (b) does not significantly harm any of the environmental objectives set out in Article 9 in accordance with Article 17;
- (c) will be carried out in compliance with the minimum safeguards laid down in Article 18; and
- (d) it complies with technical screening criteria that have been established by the Commission in accordance with Article 10(3), 11(3), 12(2), 13(2), 14(2) or 15(2).

4.1 INVESTIGATION OF ABANDONED POST-MINING AREAS TO DETERMINE LOCATIONS OF AERATION, METHANE ACCUMULATION, AND ESCAPE OF METHANE INTO VENTILATION AIR

In JSW "Pniówek" coking coal mine, four levels are maintained, two mining levels: level 830 m and level 1000 m, and two ventilation levels where mining has already been completed: level 580 m and level 705 m. The 580 m and 705 m levels are intended for liquidation, with the existing workings being used for ventilation purposes in the mine. These levels need to be prepared for proper liquidation in view of the future total mine closure (AMM). Therefore, it is necessary to carry out research that will determine the level of methane release in closed (abandoned) areas on these levels with the aim of identifying places where methane accumulates. As a result of the research, regions which will be the subject of further work will be identified. Then, the research on air migration through these regions will be carried out in order to determine the places of inflow of fresh air, places of methane accumulation, and its escape to ventilation air. In this way, places will be selected where it will be necessary to seal the rock mass, places of direct methane intake (isolation dams), and places where directional boreholes will be drilled to intake the methane accumulated there. A similar approach will be applied in Romania (Jiu Valley mines). INSEMEX - the Romanian partner (GIG's twinned institute in Romania) in REM, the scientific body and what is even more important it employs mining ventilation experts, who are familiar with all coal mine methane hazard aspects in all four operating Jiu Valley coal mines and not only Vulcan coal mine selected for REM project as it emits the largest amount of Ventilation Air Methane. The Romanian Jiu Valley underground hard coal mines are the only gassy mines left in EU (apart from Polish-ones) thus they will play important role in scalability and repeatability of the system for other European and global conditions.

In both Polish and Romanian mines, researchers will use Ventsim Design Software <https://ventsim.com/product/ventsim-advanced/>, which can be easily called solid ventilation engineer tool. The good thing and big advantage is that both partners, i.e., Polish and Romanian researchers/engineers, already have this software and feel pretty experienced and comfortable with its many years' utilisation and application to solve practical mining cases underground in their daily operations. It will facilitate the comparison of achieved results of modelling in both locations in Poland and Romania. Constructed models will be verified by drilling exploratory core boreholes (at least 3 of them in the "Pniówek" mine location) to verify/compare the real strata with the achieved model of post-mining goafs. The same core boreholes will calibrate geological and simulation models with Schlumberger Platform (Petrel, Visage, and Eclipse), whose main aim will be to locate methane accumulation places in goafs and help design long-reach directional boreholes to extract methane. The results of both modeling software will be complementary and provide complete engineering and geological information. Considering the importance of identifying "AMM sweet spots" we can not afford classical "trash in trash out" mistakes. The

possibility of performing such verification with exploratory core boreholes is another strong point of this project, as it will give an excellent basement for reliable input data.

Determination of places of methane accumulation in exploited coal seams with the use of numerical simulation models comprises two testing fields: in Poland - "Pniówek" underground hard coal (coking coal) mine and Jiu Valley bituminous coal mines in Romania.

The determination of places of methane accumulation in exploited coal seams will be performed with the most advanced available reservoir systems modeling toolkit - Schlumberger Platform (Petrel, Visage, and Eclipse). The platform combines seismic information, well data, laboratory information, and geological knowledge to build 3D methane migration and accumulation models and will be used to optimize the placement and strategy of methane drainage using long-reach directional drilling.

The modeling workflow requires the acquisition of a database of all available geological information from the study area, including archive geological reports, structural maps, geological cross-sections, borehole lithology and tectonic descriptions based on underground and surface boreholes, borehole logging data, hydrogeological data, coalbed gas content data, and the history of mining operations in the region. Besides this, the geological models will be calibrated with the new data obtained from the core material. At least two coreholes will be made from a mine gallery (in upward and downward directions) to characterize the geological and methane conditions. The core material will be fully documented with detailed lithological and tectonic descriptions of coal and adjacent sedimentary rocks, generation of borehole composite logs, and preparation of a digital image library of cores using the DMT Core Scan 3D optical scanner.

The collected core material will be subjected to petrophysical, geomechanical, and field engineering tests. The pore space analysis (porosity and pore size distribution) and absolute permeability measurements will be determined on core samples as a part of routine core analysis (RCA). The collected samples will represent different lithotypes (sandstones, mudstones, and coals) and completely different pore network development, and mechanic properties. The special core analysis (SCAL), including relative permeability in the water-gas system and X-ray microtomography (microCT), will be performed on selected samples. 3D image processing based on microCT results will serve for qualitative and quantitative characterization of samples properties. The obtained 3D models of samples and computer-based simulations will help understand the flow and mechanic properties of different lithotypes under in-situ conditions. The obtained results will be supplemented by petrographical analysis of coal samples. This will provide information about maceral composition and the distribution of microfractures and cleats that are the main pathways for gas flow in coals. The presented workflow will allow to reliably evaluate the petrophysical parameters of analyzed samples at the pore scale, which ultimately will transfer on the decrease of the uncertainty in the characterization of rock properties at a larger scale during numerical simulations.

To check potential changes of mechanical parameters of roof rock along roadways in places distant to points of core sample collection, a series of penetrometer measurements in the mining workings will be performed with density depending on locally identified changes of geological conditions.

Coal and waste gangue samples from drill cores will be collected to determine the rock and rock mass parameters appropriate for a given region. These will be mechanical parameters, including uniaxial compression strength, tensile strength, post-damage module, and residual strength, critical and total strains, Young's modulus and Poisson ratio, maximum stress values in multi-stage triaxial compression, differential and residual stress, cohesion and internal friction angle, as well as volumetric and specific weight, gangue slakeability and technological parameters – compactness of rock and workability of coal. Values of physical-mechanical and technological parameters will constitute the basis for geomechanical quality assessment of rocks and rock mass, including, among the others, floor and roof conditions of coal seams, possibility of geodynamic phenomena in the rock mass in the aspect of rock mass stability and the stability of long directional holes drilled from underground workings designated for the exploitation of the coal seam. All identified parameters will be then used as input data for numerical model development, which will be performed within this task. The tests will be carried out in accordance with European and Polish standards, ISRM recommendations, and research procedures developed based on the own experiments of the research team.

The obtained database will be used to build the simulation models (Figure 2) in the study area of the "Pniówek" coal mine. Numerical modelling will be performed in several steps including construction of geological (structural and parametric) and geomechanical (stress and strain distributions) models for the study area including exploited zones, and the construction and calibration of dynamical models of reservoir fluids (methane, water) flow. The results from the modeling will allow for determination the influence of geomechanical state evolution upon the transport properties of the structure rocks, and determination of theoretical range of the goaf methane reservoir (de-stressed zone) created as a result of mining, along with mining and geological characteristics of this area. All together will provide simulation forecasts of methane migration to exploited coal seams – location of methane accumulation places in goafs.

Figure 2. Scheme of numerical modelling

Two numerical models will be built using Ventsim Design Software: a geometric model and a flow model.

Assigning attribute parameters to individual model elements together with the mine ventilation network model.

4.2 CONSTRUCTION OF THE NUMERICAL MODEL AND CALCULATIONS IN THE FLOW MODEL.

Conducted simulations of air and methane mixture flow in selected spaces and conducted an analysis of methane source intakes from selected spaces will be the basis for determining places of methane accumulation in exploited coal seams.

For comprehensive construction of numerical calculation models of flows and determination of the source of methane emissions, the following analyses will also be carried out:

- rock mass pressure analysis,
- analysis of sources of depressions,
- analysis of characteristics of fans,
- analysis of rock mass degassing /methane drainage installations and analysis of methane drainage stations.

4.3 LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS TO DETERMINE THE CHARACTERISTICS OF GAS-COAL SYSTEM

The experiments are focused on conducting laboratory tests aimed at creating the characteristics of gas-coal system and measurements of residual methane content for the analyzed abandoned mining area. Conducting laboratory tests is aimed at obtaining the results of analyzes and parameters that will allow the creation of a database defining the comprehensive gas characteristics of coals and specific parameters affecting the development of the technology being the subject of the project. The gaseous characteristics of coal will be determined on the basis of tests of cores and drill cuttings taken from strategic places designated in specific experimental areas. To conduct the above testing, it is necessary to drill core boreholes both vertically up and down and horizontal core holes of min. 10 m in the coal seam. For the purpose of determining the coal gas characteristics, the following tests and works will be carried out:

- Determining the conditions for conducting laboratory tests in terms of determining the pressure range for the sorption isotherms and the kinetics of methane sorption, the grain class of the coal samples, the test temperature, and the type and number of drill cuttings and core samples necessary for the preparation of subsequent documentation related to gas characteristics,
- The methane-bearing capacity determination carried out on the basis of the single-phase vacuum degassing method,
- Desorption tests using the United States Bureau of Mines (USBM) method with the determination of the final methane-bearing capacity,
- Chromatographic analysis of gases obtained from degassing coal samples,
- Determination of methane sorption kinetics and sorption parameters:
 - a. effective diffusion coefficient (D_e),
 - b. sorption capacity (a),
 - c. sorption capacity in reference to dry ash free (a_{daf}),
 - d. half-time of sorption ($t_{0.5}$),
- Determination of sorption isotherms and isothermal coefficients in the Langmuir model.

Two methods will determine Methane-bearing capacity: single-phase vacuum degasification commonly used in the Polish mining industry and free desorption using the United States Bureau of Mines (USBM) method, which is used in the identification and documentation of methane deposits in hard coal seams. Conducting tests with two methods will allow for the precise determination of parameters that cannot be determined by just one method. The methane-bearing capacity in the case of single-phase vacuum degasification will be determined for core and drill cutting samples. As part of the USBM method, tests will be carried out for core samples in which the volume of desorbing gas, residual gas, and lost gas will be determined. In addition, the composition of desorbing gas and residual gas will be analyzed by gas chromatography. As part of the research, methane sorption isotherms based on the Langmuir model for selected coal samples

will be determined along with the determination of kinetics and sorption properties such as sorption capacity, effective diffusion coefficient, and half-time sorption, giving key and comprehensive information on the possibility of methane adsorption and desorption in the coal structure.

4.4 SEALING OF POST-MINING AREAS

Once the rock mass sealing areas have been selected, designs will be prepared which specify how the rock mass will be sealed in the areas described above. According to the UNECE Energy Series 71 Report (2021) one of the actions which should be taken to mitigate safety, health, and environmental risks connected to AMM is using better engineered seals. The REM project will answer that need by developing sealing agents for certain formations, which will include both high and low viscous sealing agents. Such an approach will allow deeper penetration of the sealing agent and more effective production of LRD wells even during flooding (mitigation of water fingering). Within this work, both commercial sealing fluids for coal mining industry as well as sealing fluids for oil and gas industry, adjusted for that specific need, will be examined. The development of the sealing procedure will consist of 7 stages:

- Analysis of geological conditions as well as parameters gathered in database.
- Selection of sealing fluids.
- Performing different sealing scenarios on prepared samples will imitate in situ conditions. Selection will be based on the results of permeability changes prior and after the injection procedure to samples with certain fracture width, which will imitate conditions of the “Pniówek” mine.
- Obtaining engineering parameters of selected sealing fluids
- Development of injection protocol
- Development of a technical design and sealing of goafs (JSW)
- Taking core material and checking the effectiveness of the sealing after a specified time.

Selection of proper sealing scenarios will be supported by CT visualizations and simulations of the sealing process using GeoDict software. Such an approach will increase the effectiveness of the drainage process and will allow to use that knowledge in different coal mines.

4.5 DRILLING OF LONG REACH DIRECTIONAL DRILLING (LRDD) BOREHOLES TO METHANE ACCUMULATION SITES

In this part of the project, specialised drilling operations will be carried out with long reach directional boreholes directed from underground excavations to which, after the closure of inactive levels, there will be access (in order to have the possibility of inspecting the intake locations, maintenance, and repair of measuring and regulation equipment) to the methane accumulation sites identified earlier.

There will be two types of drilling operations: first, drilling exploratory core boreholes in the “Pniówek” mine location to verify/compare the real strata with the achieved model of post-mining goafs and the second type of drilling will be Long Reach Directional Drilling (LRDD) technology (based on the application of new technology developed with RFCS support in the last years under DDMET project (INiG is DDMET project coordinator) in order to extract LCAMM from post-mining goafs.

4.6 ASSESSMENT (BALANCE) OF METHANE EMISSIONS INTO VENTILATION AIR AND INTO ATMOSPHERE

Additional work will be carried out (for Polish and Romanian mines):

- Determination of the amount of methane from selected goaf spaces, verification sources of emission to the ventilation air.
- Performing measurements of air parameters in the ventilation network and determining aerodynamic potentials in the ventilation network.
- Calculation of air flow in the ventilation network taking into account methane emission from selected goaf spaces.
- Determining the amount of methane from selected spaces captured by the methane drainage system.
- Methane balance from the drainage system and from the ventilation air in terms of verifying methane emission to the atmosphere.

The second part of the work will focus on verifying VAM flow and concentration measurements correctness presently performed by the coal mines in the shafts plus its monitoring on the surface.

Monitoring system based on UAV

The drone system is based on two DJI Matrice 350 RTK unmanned aerial vehicles and represents an advanced approach to monitoring gas emissions. The DJI Matrice 350 RTK, being a modern multifunctional platform, provides flight stability and positioning precision through the use of the RTK (Real-Time Kinematic) navigation system. This design allows for effective operations in diverse terrain and atmospheric conditions, which is crucial for efficient monitoring and control of gas pollutants.

The Matrice 350 RTK supports Waypoint, Mapping, Oblique, and Linear Flight missions. The user can utilize the Terrain Follow or Smart Oblique features for efficient data collection. In combination with the DJI Terra application, it is possible to quickly obtain digital 2D and 3D results, allowing for precise and efficient terrain mapping.

The first drone in the system will be equipped with an advanced laser methane detector. The use of this technology enables precise and rapid detection of methane presence in the air, which is crucial both for environmental protection and for preventing potential threats to public health and

infrastructure. Thanks to the detection capabilities of this system, it is possible to quickly locate sources of methane emissions, allowing for an effective response to potential leaks or other failures.

Figure 3 Matrice 350 RTK Drone with optical sensor

The second drone is equipped with a mobile air pollution monitoring system known as SnifferD (Figure 4). This advanced system not only detects various gases but also accurately maps their concentrations in real-time. It utilizes a range of highly sensitive gas sensors, allowing for accurate identification and measurement of different chemical substances in the atmosphere. Thanks to the mobility and rapid response of the drone equipped with SnifferD, effective monitoring of areas with potentially varying environmental conditions, such as industrial sites, landfills, or rural areas, is possible where the presence of gases may result from various factors, including natural and anthropogenic processes.

Together, these two drones constitute a comprehensive gas monitoring system, enabling quick identification, localization, and mapping of air pollutants. Their versatility and effectiveness make them invaluable tools for both environmental protection agencies and industrial companies striving to minimize the negative impact of their activities on the natural environment.

Figure 4 Drone equipped with SnifferD

Description of field experiment site at Experimental mine „Barbara”

The major source of coal mine methane emissions is VAM (Ventilation Air Methane), vented to the atmosphere via the return shafts from underground hard coal mines. Consequently, when considering verification of VAM emissions, the points of our interest are the return shafts. Figure 5 presents a typical cross-section of the return shaft. In this particular case, it is the return shaft located next door at Experimental mine “Barbara” in Mikołów.

Figure 5. Illustrative drawing of a field test at the Experimental mine „Barbara” (department of GIG)

Unique advantage of EM “Barbara” location is that can be gassy only on demand! It means that we can perform background tests first in a methane-free environment, which is practically impossible in operating mines. After these tests and elaboration of novel methodology, it should be fairly easy to convince individual mines’ management and Mining Authority to approach operating mines. It is needless to say that we have inimitable opportunity to elaborate and test a very accurate methodology, which could be applied globally in the mining sector. We hope that this should be in line with EC and UNEP IMEO targets to be achieved.

4.7 CONSTRUCTION OF A PARALLEL GAS DRAINAGE SYSTEM WITH REDUCED (LOW) METHANE CONCENTRATION

In "Pniówek" coking coal mine there is a methane drainage system, which drains methane from mine workings and post-mining goafs with an average methane concentration in the captured gas of at least 45%. It results from current possibilities of economic use of methane obtained in this way. Cogeneration systems for production of electric and heat energy from extracted gas work effectively at methane concentration in gas above 45% (minimum 40%). As described, the expected methane concentration in gas captured from the abandoned part of the mine (post-mining goafs) will be in the range of 20 to 40% (above explosive range !).

The predicted concentration is based on measurements carried out to date. In order to capture and transport this gas to the surface, it will be necessary to install a "parallel" gas drainage system with reduced methane concentration in the captured gas. According to Polish regulations, the methane concentration at the compressor station must be at least 30%. Therefore, the construction of this system will require the execution of a project including the construction, on special terms approved by the Higher Mining Authority, of a surface methane compressor station, a network of underground pipelines to the methane intake locations, methane intakes from directional boreholes and behind isolation dams with automatic measurements of the composition and quantity of the captured gas as well as with the possibility of automatic control at these intakes. Construction and installation work will be carried out on the basis of this project.

4.8 CONSTRUCTION OF GAS ENGINES TO PRODUCE ELECTRICITY FROM EXTRACTED METHANE

The gas recovered from the post-mining goafs with a methane concentration of 20 to 40% through the parallel drainage system should be utilised. The most economically effective way to utilise methane captured through the drainage system is to use it as a fuel in gas engines coupled with an electricity generator. This solution makes it possible to produce electricity directly. The solutions used so far make it possible to produce electricity in gas engines with up to 4 MWe power. In comparison, 1 MWe requires the supply of approx. 4 Nm³ of methane (calculated as a pure component) with a minimum methane concentration of 40% in the supplied gas. Due to low methane concentration (20 to 40%), the proposed solution requires special adjustments of the engines to operate at a reduced methane concentration. Therefore, it will be necessary to implement a special design and installation dedicated to this project. It was already discussed with gas engines producers. Needless to say, the excitement about this new innovative solution is on both sides.

The above description of the methodology confirms what was already mentioned that the REM project was prepared to be simple but very effective to achieve its smart targets.

5 IMPACT

The innovative value delivered by REM is based on the following aspects:

1. It is the first comprehensive attempt at an European/worldwide scale to identify methane accumulation locations in abandoned parts (already exploited) of the coal mines' reservoirs for its capture by a reduced methane content installation - less than 30% and effective utilization to produce energy.
2. It will give guidance for policy and coal mine decision-makers in order to select such methane accumulation locations in abandoned parts of the coal mines' reservoirs to have better control over underground methane emissions.
3. It will increase the underground labour safety conditions, effectively mitigate coal mine methane emissions to the atmosphere, generate economical benefits from produced energy, reduce costs and fees for methane emissions.
4. It will improve overall public welfare and healthy standards, and by giving information on the environmental and social cost-effectiveness of these actions as well by demonstrating the opportunities that coal mining sites have to improve will smooth out transition period of mining sector.
5. It will enhance simultaneously the delivery of the following EU policies by the coal mining industry: waste management policy (Directive 2006/21/EC), climate and energy policies (COM/2016/0479 final).

Repeatability and scalability of REM project - reducing methane emissions to the atmosphere from ventilation air using an AMM capture facility with a concentration below 30%.

Key variables

- ✓ Mine model - number of development levels, already mined coal seams and abandoned (closed) mining areas
- ✓ Availability of closed mining areas - possibility of sealing them and subsequently capturing methane
- ✓ Residual methane potential of post-mining goafs 2.

Repeatability

- ✓ For mines with a similar model (several levels and closed areas within which there is a group of exploited coal seams with high methane concentration and off-balance coal seams located in the impact zone)
- ✓ Under elaborated project the key tasks will be elaborated (important order) according to which the project can be implemented in other locations

Scalability

- ✓ In subsequent implementations, it is possible to scale up the investment after the first steps (tasks) including research have been completed:
 - construction of a geological model with determination of residual methane content,
 - identification of abandoned mining space/methane reservoirs with reduced methane concentration,
 - building a spatial and flow model of methane in abandoned mining space/methane reservoirs and mine ventilation network,
 - measurement of residual methane content in abandoned mining/methane reservoirs in rock mass,
 - identification of methane migration, flow testing with tracer gases,
 - concentration and pressure measurements at the boundary of methane reservoirs.

The above studies will allow estimating the size of the methane intake and thus the scale of the project. Based on the research it will be possible to:

- identifying where and how to seal abandoned areas,
- determination of gas capture locations in underground workings,
- elaborating a design for the installation - diameters and lengths of pipelines,
- determining the operating parameters of the methane drainage station, including its capacity,
- determining the number and power of gas engines that the captured methane can power.

JSW coking coal mines with similar mining and geological conditions

- ✓ KWK „Borynia-Zofiówka” Ruch Zofiówka – the closest,
- ✓ KWK „Budryk”
- ✓ KWK „Knurów-Szczygłowie” Ruch Szczygłowie

Other coal mines with similar mining and geological conditions

- ✓ „Brzeszcze” coal mine
- ✓ „Sośnica” coal mine
- ✓ „ROW” coal mine
- ✓ „Staszic-Wujek” coal mine
- ✓ „Mysłowice-Wesoła” coal mine
- ✓ All coal mines belonging to Czech mining concern OKD,
- ✓ „Jiu Valley coal mines” in Romania,
- ✓ „Moonidih” coal mine in India.

6 SUMMARY

The REM project is expected to produce highly practical results, reaching a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 8. The research component will be minimal, focusing on achieving specific goals. The project will yield tangible technical solutions and equipment, including methodologies for identifying methane accumulation in post-mining goafs, detecting rock mass leaks where coal has been extracted, sealing mine goafs, and drilling directional boreholes to maximize methane extraction. It will also involve the installation of systems to transport low-concentration methane from goafs to surface compressor stations through monitored underground pipelines and adapting surface compressor stations and engines to work with low-concentration methane.

Additionally, the project will construct and test monitoring and control equipment at the EM "Barbara" testing ground to detect methane emissions from mine shafts and existing pipelines and conduct further measurements at the "Pniówek" coking coal mine.

The primary beneficiaries will be mining operations, gaining increased workplace safety, cost savings from capturing and utilizing low-concentration methane for local electricity and heat generation, and reduced penalties for methane emissions. Using gas engines to burn methane rather than releasing it will lower greenhouse gas emissions, promoting environmental and health benefits, as methane emission and ozone layer depletion are linked to serious health risks.

The development of prototype devices for low-concentration methane will advance scientific disciplines such as mining aerology, drilling, geology, fluid mechanics, thermodynamics, physics, and automation. This will generate new knowledge and strengthen scientific tools and computational systems.

Implementing REM project solutions is expected to introduce new equipment in the gas industry based on patented technologies, create jobs, spread process solutions across other mines and countries, foster technology export, and enhance training and reskilling. These advancements will improve industrial process optimization and safety standards, reduce operating costs, increase profitability for mines and producers in the mining sector, and decrease CO₂ emissions. They will also enhance workplace safety by minimizing risks of methane-related incidents and contribute to UNECE partners' efforts to improve legislation and raise consumer awareness.

While the REM project appears overwhelmingly positive with no apparent environmental, regulatory, economic, social, or health drawbacks, potential risks arising from the geopolitical situation in Eastern Europe could influence steel and energy prices, affecting project costs. Project partners are aware of these issues and plan to expedite procurement processes to mitigate these risks.